

Emotion regulation mediates between self-compassion and depressive symptoms

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Self-compassion has been consistently associated with greater well-being and lower levels of mental health problems, including depression. However, the mechanisms that explain the connection between self-compassion and depressive symptoms are still not well understood. One possible mechanism is emotion regulation. This study examined whether two types of emotion regulation strategies, one considered maladaptive (expressive suppression) and one considered adaptive (cognitive reappraisal), act as mediators in the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. A stratified probability sample of 300 Hong Kong Chinese adults aged 18 to 70 years was recruited. Mediation analysis was conducted using PROCESS version 4.2 for SPSS. Expressive suppression significantly mediated the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms, with a coefficient of $b = -0.07$ and a confidence interval ranging from -0.12 to -0.03 . In contrast, cognitive reappraisal did not show a significant mediating effect, with a coefficient of $b = 0.01$ and a confidence interval ranging from -0.05 to 0.07 . These results suggest that higher levels of self-compassion are linked to lower levels of depressive symptoms through a reduced tendency to use expressive suppression. Emotion regulation may therefore play an important role in the influence of self-compassion on mental health. Future research should explore these processes using longitudinal designs to understand how they develop over time.

Keywords: cognitive reappraisal; depressive symptoms; emotion regulation; expressive suppression; self-compassion

Depression is a significant contributor to global disease burden and is the leading cause of disability (Feigin, 2016). Its prevalence has been increasing in recent decades, with lifetime rates ranging from 20%–25% in women and 7% to 12% in men. Depression has a profound impact on quality of life and survival, accounting for approximately 50% of psychiatric consultations and 12% of hospital admissions (Kuo et al., 2015). Given the importance of understanding factors that protect against depression, self-compassion has obtained significant attention from researchers and practitioners (Conversano et al., 2020). It is believed to function as a protective factor against depression by influencing how individuals deal with distressing situations. Additionally, emotion regulation is proposed as a potential mechanism through which self-compassion operates to shield against depression (Ferrari et al., 2019).

In 2003, Neff introduced a model and created a self-compassion measure that draws from Buddhist principles emphasising the importance of showing compassion to oneself and others for overall well-being (Neff, 2003a, 2003b). The self-compassion framework consists of three main components, each encompassing both positive and negative aspects. The first component entails being kind and caring towards oneself while refraining from self-criticism and rejection. The second component involves acknowledging one's own experiences as part of the shared human experience, fostering a sense of common humanity rather than feelings of isolation or separation. The third component involves cultivating mindful awareness, enabling acceptance of both negative and positive thoughts and emotions without attempting to alter or evade them.

Previous studies have consistently shown the negative association between self-compassion and depressive symptoms (e.g., Körner et al., 2015; López et al., 2018; Neff, 2003a). Patients with major depressive disorder have been found to have lower levels of self-compassion compared to individuals who have never experienced depression (Diedrich et al., 2017; Krieger et al., 2013). One longitudinal study demonstrated that decreased self-compassion predicts higher levels of depressive symptoms, indicating that low self-compassion may increase the risk of depression (Krieger et al., 2016). Self-compassion may protect against depression by reducing negative thinking styles and increasing positive emotions. Low levels of self-compassion have also been associated with depression recurrence (Ehret et al., 2015). And self-criticism, an indicative of low self-compassion, has been identified as a vulnerability factor for depressive disorder (Joeng & Turner, 2015). These studies implied that enhancing self-compassion may be particularly important for individuals vulnerable to depressive symptoms. Therefore, understanding how self-compassion operates in the general population and its influence on depressive symptoms is crucial.

Despite the consistent association between self-compassion and depression, there is a lack of understanding regarding the specific pathways that link them. One potential pathway is emotion regulation, which refers to the ability to consciously influence the types and expression of emotions (Gross, 2015). Difficulty with emotion regulation has been identified as a predictive and sustaining factor in depression (Dryman & Heimberg, 2018). Effective emotion regulation involves managing and responding to negative emotions, replacing them with more positive experiences. In contrast, deficits in emotion regulation, particularly in down-regulating negative affect, are believed to be fundamental to mood disorders (Joormann & Stanton, 2016). Ineffective emotion regulation can also lead to persistent distress and ultimately depressive symptoms (Dryman & Heimberg, 2018). Considering that self-compassion involves a shift in how individuals approach painful experiences and negative emotions (Neff, 2003a), it is proposed that individuals with higher levels of self-compassion may exhibit more effective emotion regulation, leading to a reduction in depressive symptoms. Self-compassion may also influence specific emotion regulation strategies that individuals vulnerable to depression tend to either excessively rely on or underutilise (Ferrari et al., 2019; Finlay-Jones, 2017). It may decrease the use of maladaptive emotion regulation strategies and enhance the use of adaptive ones. Research has shown an inverse relationship between self-compassion and difficulty with emotion regulation, leading to decreased depressive symptoms (e.g., Ferrari et al., 2019; Finlay-Jones, 2017; Finlay-Jones et al., 2015).

Substantial research highlights the key role of emotion regulation in the onset and maintenance of psychopathology, particularly depressive disorders (Aldao et al., 2010). While specific regulatory strategies may vary across disorders, there are common emotional processes that account for much of the overlap among depressive disorders (Aldao et al., 2010). In particular, these common emotional processes typically involve the interplay between emotional experiences – such as the content, intensity, and duration of emotions, as well as adaptive and maladaptive emotion regulation strategies. For instance, Hofmann et al. (2012) propose that increased negative emotion, problematic

emotion regulation, and a deficiency in positive emotion are mutually reinforcing factors contributing to the development of chronic emotional disorders. Meanwhile, Mennin et al. (2007) emphasise the critical role of heightened emotional intensity, poor emotional understanding, negative reactivity to emotions, and maladaptive emotional responses in increasing vulnerability to depression.

According to the Revised Process Model of Emotion Regulation (RPMER; Gross, 2015), an emotional state is triggered when a situation is assessed as immediately relevant to one's goals. Emotion regulation is utilised to influence the process of emotion generation, which occurs in a series of cycles. According to the RPMER, there are five distinct groups of emotion regulation strategies that affect various stages within the emotion generation cycle (Gross, 2015). These strategies encompass situation selection, situation modification, attentional deployment, cognitive change, and response modulation. The first two strategies, situation selection and situation modification, are implemented at the beginning of the cycle and involve efforts to control the environment. Attentional deployment, the third strategy, centres on redirecting an individual's attention in emotionally evoking situations. The remaining two strategies take place during the appraisal and response phases of the cycle. Cognitive change encompasses cognitive reappraisal, a technique aiming to transform negative emotions into neutral or positive ones. Cognitive reappraisal involves reframing an experience to regulate emotional distress (Dryman & Heimberg, 2018) and alter the emotional impact of distressing events by shifting negative cognitive biases (Gross & John, 2003). It is applied early in the emotion regulation process, before a behavioural response to the emotion is fully determined.

In contrast, response modulation strategies occur later in the process and involve regulating the behavioural expression of emotions after they have been generated (Gross, 2015). One such response modulation strategy is expressive suppression, which refers to an individual's attempts to conceal positive or negative emotional experiences from others. However, expressive suppression is generally unhelpful for individuals experiencing depression. Previous studies have indicated that when individuals try to hide observable emotions, it can actually intensify negative emotions instead of reducing them, as it leads to increased negatively focused self-consciousness (Jazaieri et al., 2015). Expressive suppression also diminishes the intensity of positive emotions in social situations (Lalot et al., 2014). Furthermore, a systematic review conducted by Inwood and Ferrari (2018) identified five relevant studies on other mental health conditions, all of which reported negative associations between self-compassion and dysfunctional emotional regulation. For example, dysfunctional emotional regulation has been found to mediate the relationship between self-compassion and depressive disorder (Diedrich et al., 2017). Additionally, dysfunctional emotional regulation has been identified as a mediating factor in the relationship between self-compassion and post-traumatic stress symptoms in a student sample (Barlow et al., 2017). Conversely, Scoglio et al. (2015) found that self-compassion mediated the relationship between dysfunctional emotional regulation and PTSD symptoms. Inwood and Ferrari (2018) concluded that the diverse findings suggest that the relationship between self-compassion and emotional regulation may vary across populations and mental health conditions, warranting further investigation. In summary, these two emotion regulation strategies may elucidate the connection between self-compassion and depressive symptoms, underscoring the need for further exploration.

One way that self-compassion may protect against depressive symptoms by influencing individuals' tendency to engage in expressive suppression, which involves concealing emotional experiences from others. While suppression may be initially protective or adaptive in that people do not experience immediate pain or distress, over time suppression can become maladaptive, leading to further negative affect (Beblo et al., 2012) and worsening depressive symptoms (Sarfan et al., 2019) and long-term emotional difficulties (Joormann & Stanton, 2016). Mindfulness, a facet of self-compassion, counteracts expressive suppression by encouraging individuals to turn towards distress rather than avoid it, which fosters a more adaptive relationship with negative emotions (Desrosiers et al., 2013).

Another way self-compassion may protect against depression is by increasing the capacity to use cognitive reappraisal, an adaptive emotion regulation strategy associated with reduced depressive symptoms (Dryman & Heimberg, 2018). Self-compassion encompasses the perspective of perceiving negative emotions or experiences as a natural part of the human condition, emphasising the concept of common humanity, and results in alleviate feelings of disconnection and isolation (Finlay-Jones, 2017). It also involves reframing emotional experiences with increased mindfulness and self-kindness, potentially leading to reductions in depressive symptoms (Garland et al., 2015; Neff, 2003b). Individuals with high self-compassion may engage in more accurate appraisals of self-

evaluations and think about distressing events in ways that minimise their negative impact (Donald et al., 2018; Trompetter et al., 2017). One experimental study has shown that combining self-compassion with cognitive reappraisal is more effective in reducing depressive symptoms compared to using cognitive reappraisal alone among a sample of people with depression (Diedrich et al., 2016).

In this study, we aimed to investigate whether two emotion regulation strategies, one maladaptive (i.e., expressive suppression) and one adaptive (i.e., cognitive reappraisal), mediate the association between self-compassion and depressive symptoms in a sample of adults across different age groups. We examined these relationships using mediation analysis. Our overall expectation was that higher levels of self-compassion would be associated with lower levels of depressive symptoms. And then our study hypothesised that (H1) expressive suppression and (H2) cognitive reappraisal would mediate the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms.

METHOD

Study design and data collection

Upon obtaining potential participants' initial verbal consent, researchers will confirm their eligibility, explain the nature of the study, and obtain their written informed consent. A cross-sectional population-based survey were conducted by stratified probability sampling from a database representative of the population (Census and Statistics Department, 2021) upon obtaining the written consent from respondents. Inclusion criteria were (1) Chinese ethnicity, (2) Cantonese fluency (the most commonly spoken Chinese language and the mother tongue of 90% of the population in Hong Kong), and (3) elementary education level or above. Individuals with histories of psychiatric conditions and presence of cognitive impairments were excluded from the study. Participants were then required to complete the questionnaires, which typically takes approximately 30 minutes of their time.

Measures

Demographic characteristics. A standardised form was used to obtain respondents' demographic information including age, sex, education level, employment status and monthly household income.

Self-compassion. The 26-item Self-Compassion Scale (SCS; Neff, 2003b) assessed six sub-components of self-compassion: self-kindness, self-judgment, common humanity, isolation, mindfulness, and over-identification. The SCS score is the average of the six subscales scores and ranges from 1 to 5, with higher scores indicating higher levels of self-compassion.

Depressive symptoms. The 20-item Center for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale (CES-D; Radloff, 1977) is a widely-used population measure of depressive symptoms with good psychometric properties. Participants rated how frequently they had experienced symptoms within the previous week (e.g., "I had crying spells," "I was bothered by things that usually don't bother me") on a scale from 0 (rarely or none of the time/less than 1 day) to 3 (all of the time/5–7 days). Total score ranges from 0 to 60. Higher scores indicating higher levels of depressive symptoms.

Emotion regulation. The 10-item Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ; Gross & John, 2003) assessed the emotional regulation strategies of Expressive Suppression (four items) and Cognitive Reappraisal (six items). Respondents rate the items from 1 "strongly disagree" to 7 "strongly agree". Total scores were obtained for each participant by averaging his/her responses to the items, with higher scores indicating higher levels of expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal representatively.

Data analyses

The major goal of the present study was to investigate how expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal mediate the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. This study intended to select one maladaptive and one adaptive emotion regulation strategy to examine how they mediate the association between self-compassion and depressive symptoms in a sample of adults across different age groups. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of two commonly studied and representative strategies: expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal. First, descriptive data analyses and Pearson correlations were conducted using SPSS 27.0 to examine the associations among the variables.

Second, the mediation model was analysed through the utilisation of PROCESS version 4.2 for SPSS, developed by Hayes (2017). Two mediation hypotheses were tested using Hayes' Model 4. In the PROCESS, 5000 bootstraps were performed, and a confidence interval (CI) of 95% was employed to estimate the effects. Instead, the distribution is empirically constructed. Based on this generated sampling distribution, 95% confidence intervals are constructed to assess the significance of the indirect effects. The significance of these effects is determined by whether the value zero falls within the upper and lower confidence intervals (Preacher & Hayes, 2008). If the value zero is not encompassed by the confidence intervals, the effects are considered statistically significant.

Third, multiple mediation model was re-examined by exclusively utilising the positive subscales of the SCS, namely self-kindness, mindfulness, and common humanity. The rationale for this approach stems from previous research suggesting that the negative scales of the SCS may conceptually overlap with psychopathology and related constructs, such as rumination (Muris & Otgaar, 2020). By excluding the negative SCS scales and re-running the multiple mediation model, we can assess whether our findings remain consistent without the potential influence of conceptually overlapping scales.

RESULTS

Sociodemographic statistics

This study consisted of 300 participants ($M = 42.90$ years, $SD = 15.47$). Half was female. Sixteen received primary education, 145 received secondary education, and 139 received tertiary education or above. Reported average monthly household income ranged from \leq HK \$10,000 (10%), \$10,001–\$20,000 (16%), \$20,001–\$30,000 (18%), \$30,001–\$40,000 (24%), to $>$ \$40,000 (32%), with US \$1 approximately equivalent to HK \$7.80. Of the 300 participants, 59% reported being full-time employed, 25% reported being part-time employed, 1% reported being unemployed, 5% reported that they were housewives, and 10% reported that they were retired.

Preliminary analyses

First, data were screened for “missingness” and no item responses were missing. No missing data were found in the current study. Subsequently, outlier screening was done through the utilisation of boxplots and scatterplots. No significant outliers were identified. And the distributions of all scales demonstrated normality. Descriptive statistics and correlations for all variables investigated in the study were explored and are presented in Table 1. Notably, all variables exhibited significant correlations with each other in the expected directions. Specifically, self-compassion displayed a moderate negative association with depressive symptoms ($r = -0.54$, $p < 0.001$), as expected.

Table 1
Bivariate correlations and descriptive statistics for study variables

Variable	1	2	3	4
Self-compassion	–			
Depressive symptoms	–0.54**	–		
Expressive suppression	–0.39**	0.36**	–	
Cognitive reappraisal	0.47**	–0.24**	–0.21**	–
<i>M</i>	3.24	10.87	3.09	4.74
<i>SD</i>	0.41	3.28	0.88	1.00
<i>Alpha</i>	0.90	0.94	0.94	0.78

* $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.001$

Mediation models

To assess the mediating effects of each emotion regulation strategy, while controlling for other emotion regulation strategies, a multiple mediation model was employed (see Figure 1). When expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal were included, only expressive suppression significantly mediated the link between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. Confirming the first hypothesis, the results indicate that expressive suppression significantly mediated the association between self-compassion and depressive symptoms, $b = -0.07$, 95% CI $[-0.12, -0.03]$. Expressive suppression accounted for 29% of the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. However, contrary to our second hypothesis, cognitive reappraisal did not exhibit significant mediation in the link between self-compassion and depressive symptoms, $b = 0.01$, 95% CI $[-0.05, 0.07]$. Table 2 summarises the above results.

Table 2
Standardised coefficients for mediation models examining association between self-compassion and depressive symptoms

Dependent variable (DV)	Mediator (M)	Effect of IV on M (a)	Effect of M on DV (b)	Direct effect (c)	Indirect effect (a x b)	Indirect effect 95% CI	Total effect (c)
	Total effect			–0.48***			–0.54***
Depressive symptoms	Expressive suppression	–0.39***	0.18**		–0.07	–0.12 to –0.03	
	Cognitive reappraisal	0.47***	0.02		0.01	–0.05 to 0.07	

IV = self-compassion; italicised confidence intervals do not include zero, indicating a significant indirect effect

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Figure 1

Hypothesised mediation model between self-compassion and depressive symptoms

By exclusively utilising the positive subscales of the SCS, the overall association between self-compassion and depressive symptoms was slightly weaker, however remained moderately negatively correlated ($r = -0.35, p < 0.001$). It is noteworthy that in line with our initial multiple-mediation model, expressive suppression was found to significantly mediate the relationship between self-compassion (measured using the three positive subscales) and depressive symptoms, $b = -0.07, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.11, -0.03]$. However, cognitive reappraisal, $b = 0.00, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.03, 0.03]$, did not show significant mediation. Expressive suppression accounted for 12% of the association between self-compassion (positive scales) and depressive symptoms. These findings suggest that regardless of whether the total score on the self-compassion scale or only the positive subscale scores were considered, expressive suppression emerged as a significant mediator between self-compassion and depressive symptoms in our sample. Consistent with our initial operationalisation of self-compassion in this study, we chose to maintain Neff's conceptualisation of an overall level of self-compassion (Neff et al., 2017) and interpreted the results using the total score on the self-compassion scale.

DISCUSSION

The current study aimed to investigate the mediating role of emotional regulation on the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. Consistent with previous research (e.g., Körner et al., 2015; López et al., 2018), self-compassion was found to have a strong association with depressive symptoms. While prior studies have focused on decreased self-compassion in individuals with major depressive disorder (Diedrich et al., 2017), this study extends the literature by demonstrating that higher levels of self-compassion are associated with lower depressive symptomatology in the general public. While the current findings are based on a cross-sectional study design, earlier research has provided support for the proposed temporal sequence (Diedrich et al., 2017; Krieger et al., 2016). However, it remains plausible that depressive symptoms themselves have a further impact on individuals' capacity for self-compassion, subsequently placing them at an elevated risk for depression, akin to the scar theories of recurrent depression. As such, longitudinal research is needed to better understand the temporal relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. Nevertheless, it seems self-compassion plays a clear role in diminishing depressive symptoms (MacBeth & Gumley, 2012).

Emotion regulation strategies were also found to play a significant role in the impact of self-compassion on depressive symptoms (Ferrari et al., 2019; Finlay-Jones, 2017). Specifically, higher levels of self-compassion were associated with lower levels of depressive symptoms through reduced use of expressive suppression. Our study contributes to the existing body of literature by illustrating an overall pathway through which self-compassion may influence depressive symptomatology, by exerting an influence on emotion regulation strategies. These findings build upon the existing clinical research that suggests higher levels of self-compassion serve as a protective factor against depression by enhancing individuals' ability to regulate negative emotions (Diedrich et al., 2017; Krieger et al., 2013). Notably, the mediation model revealed that expressive suppression emerged as the significant mediator, surpassing cognitive reappraisal. When individuals encounter stress or challenging emotions, self-compassion can act as a means of relating to these experiences, encouraging them to approach distress rather than avoid it. This is important because suppressing emotions is a problematic emotion regulation strategy that results in a higher risk of developing subsequent episodes of depression (Joormann & Stanton, 2016). Our findings align with previous research conducted on a clinical sample, which examined expressive suppression as a mediator between self-compassion and depressive symptoms (Liu et al., 2023). Other studies have also indicated that self-compassion's tendency to conceal emotional experiences from others leads to negative mental health outcomes (Paucsik et al., 2023). This implies that self-compassion may mitigate depressive symptoms by reducing the inclination to conceal emotional experiences from others. In turn, this may alleviate depressive symptoms.

An unexpected outcome of our study was the cognitive reappraisal was not the significant mediator in the association between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. This finding contradicts recent experimental research, which demonstrated that the preliminary use of self-compassion enhanced the explicit use of cognitive reappraisal, leading to a significant reduction in depressed mood among individuals with clinical depression (Diedrich et al., 2017). Our mediation model did indicate a significant pathway between self-compassion and cognitive reappraisal, suggesting that individuals with higher levels of self-compassion may possess a greater capacity for engaging in cognitive reappraisal of situations. However, the impact of cognitive reappraisal on depressive symptoms did not reach significance. This aligns with several prior studies that have indicated a less consistent association between cognitive reappraisal and depressive symptoms compared to other emotion regulation strategies (Aldao & Nolen-Hoeksema, 2010; Troy et al., 2010). Our findings suggest that cognitive reappraisal may not play a prominent role in how self-compassion influences depressive symptoms. This may be because there are instances when it is more adaptive to alter the relationship with inner experiences, including emotions, thoughts, and physical sensations, rather than relying solely on traditional cognitive modification strategies (Diedrich et al., 2017; Gotlib & Joormann, 2010). Thus, the process of transforming one's relationship with experiences through self-compassion may not primarily rely on cognitive reappraisal. Instead, it may involve a shift in how individuals engage with their experiences, such as accepting them, which subsequently influences depressive symptoms.

The efficacy of cognitive reappraisal can depend on the context and individual differences. For instance, one study found that self-compassion enhanced the effectiveness of cognitive reappraisal in reducing depressed mood among individuals with major depressive disorder (Diedrich et al., 2016). However, cognitive reappraisal may not always be an effective strategy for everyone, particularly

since the participants in the current study are from the general population rather than a clinical sample with depressive disorders. The lack of mediation observed in this study suggests that cognitive reappraisal may not have been an optimal strategy for the specific sample and context examined. Furthermore, the RPMEER model of emotional regulation suggests that cognitive reappraisal occurs early in the emotion cycle and involves changing the meaning of a situation to regulate emotions (Gross, 2015). However, reframing the meaning of an event through cognitive reappraisal is a challenging task that requires significant conscious mental effort (Troy et al., 2018). Milyavsky et al. (2019) have demonstrated that the utilisation of cognitive reappraisal is influenced by the motivation to employ it and the perceived difficulty of doing so. In this regard, self-compassion serves as a motivator for engaging in reappraisal of a situation, but it does not directly impact the perceived difficulty of the task. It is worth noting the strong correlation found both in our study and recent experimental evidence between cognitive reappraisal and self-compassion, suggesting that self-compassion facilitates the use of cognitive reappraisal to reduce depressive symptoms (Diedrich et al., 2016). Therefore, further investigation is necessary to gain a clearer understanding and provide clarification through future research.

CONCLUSION

There are some limitations that should be taken into consideration when evaluating the findings. Firstly, it is important to note that the data collected for this study were cross-sectional and relied on self-report measures. The using of self-report measures in this study introduces the potential for common method biases, which could have influenced the findings (Podsakoff et al., 2003). To address these biases, future research could consider incorporating alternative assessment methods, such as clinical interviews or reports from significant others. Although our findings are consistent with previous longitudinal studies that support the temporal order proposed in our model (Diedrich et al., 2017; Krieger et al., 2016), it is important to acknowledge that the cross-sectional design of our study prevents us from establishing a definitive temporal sequence. It is still possible, however, that depression itself further impacts people's ability to be self-compassionate, which subsequently puts them at increased risk for recurrent depression. This limitation arises from the inability to observe the mediation between variables over time (Cole & Maxwell, 2003; Relojo, 2016). Given the inherent biases associated with cross-sectional mediation analyses (Maxwell & Cole, 2007), it is crucial for future research to examine our model longitudinally. By investigating the variables using a longitudinal method, we can draw causal inferences and stronger conclusions that self-compassion significantly predicts depressive symptoms beyond different time points, as well as specify which time points it predicts. Moreover, the mediating effects of emotion regulation strategies may vary at different time points. Such longitudinal investigations would offer a more comprehensive understanding of these processes as they unfold over time.

The current study has a notable strength in its use of a large sample size with equal numbers of male and female participants. However, it is important to acknowledge that the sample obtained was non-clinical in nature, which limits the generalisability of the results to individuals with psychological disorders. Therefore, replication of the findings with clinical samples is necessary to establish their applicability in those populations. Certain clinical populations, such as ethnic minorities, LGBTQ individuals, and those with low socioeconomic status, are often underrepresented in research. Actively recruiting these groups and examining self-compassion in relation to depression could help address disparities in mental health research and treatment. Examining the predictive relationships in individuals with psychological disorders is particularly crucial, as they face greater challenges in effectively employing emotional regulation, and the correlation patterns of self-compassion are less distinctly established in this group (Finlay-Jones, 2017). Confirming similar predictive relationships in clinical samples would have significant implications for informing clinical interventions.

Despite its limitations, the present research sheds light on the potential mechanisms through which self-compassion operates in individuals with depressive symptoms. This work provides a foundation for future research to expand upon, offering valuable insights for considering clinical interventions aimed at enhancing self-compassion for the prevention and treatment of major depressive disorders. For instance, it would be beneficial to examine established programs focused on self-compassion, such as Mindful Self-Compassion (Neff et al., 2020) and Compassion Focused Therapy (Gilbert, 2014), within samples of individuals with major depressive disorder. Testing the efficacy of these programs in such populations could provide valuable information for intervention strategies. Furthermore, given the influence of self-compassion on emotion regulation, it is important for future research to investigate additional emotion regulation strategies such as savouring and

acceptance that may contribute to the positive effects of self-compassion on mental health. Understanding the relationships between self-compassion and other psychological disorders characterised by difficulties in emotion regulation would be a valuable area of investigation. Ultimately, self-compassion appears to be a significant component of mental health in general populations, and further research exploring its role in addressing psychological disorders, including recurrent depression and anxiety disorders, holds great potential for improving clinical outcomes.

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